

Electrical and optical properties of LSMO/Monolayer MoS₂ photodiodes

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Two dimensional (2D) transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) and artificial van der Waals heterostructures made from these materials have been experimentally and theoretically investigated as promising candidates for novel photovoltaic and optoelectronic devices due to their excellent optical and electrical properties^[1,2]. Very recently, many experimental efforts have been made on the fabrication and study of 2D-2D heterostructures, like for example MoS₂-WS₂ and graphene-MoS₂^[3,4] and 2D-3D heterostructures, such as graphene-Si. Nevertheless, the interaction between two dimensional material and transition metal complex oxides has not been largely investigated so far. In this work, we investigate heterostructures made of 3D lanthanum strontium manganite oxide (LSMO) and 2D monolayer MoS₂ and report their photodiode behavior.

Here, we report the photodiode behavior in LSMO (p type)/monolayer MoS₂ (n type) heterostructures fabricated by deterministic transfer of mechanically exfoliated flake and transferred to LSMO^[5]. Under illumination, an obvious photocurrent (and photovoltage) is generated by the photovoltaic effect. The photocurrent and photoresponsivity are dependent both on the incident light wavelength and power density. The device displays short-circuit currents up to 0.4 nA and open-circuit voltages up to 400 mV. Measuring as a function of incident optical power density, we

find that the open-circuit voltage and short-circuit current depend linearly and logarithmically, respectively, on power density, confirming an ideal photodiode behavior.

In conclusion, we have investigated the electrical and optoelectronic properties of LSMO/monolayer MoS₂ heterostructures. Our work may benefit to the integration of two-dimensional materials with metal complex oxides. This might contribute to developments in the area of van der Waals heterostructures and it will provide novel applications in electronics and optoelectronics.

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